

RELIGION BELIEFS AND EATING DISORDERS

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Abstract

Researchers are looking at a variety of risk factors, since there is not one single component that leads to eating disorders. In addition, they are investigating how the many risk factors are connected to one another. In addition, researchers have started looking at preventative and interventional measures that may be used to stop an eating problem from progressing to a severe level. On the other hand, owing to the intricacy of EDs, no treatment strategy has been shown to be effective. A discussion of the factors that may have a role in the development of eating disorders. Even while a substantial number of the elements that have a role in the symptomology of eating disorders are now well understood, there are additional aspects that need more research. An unhealthy preoccupation with one's body image, a feeling of helplessness, a history of sexual abuse, an obsession with attaining perfection, and worries about one's gender are all risk factors that have been linked to the development of eating disorders (Bruch, 1973; Franko & Striegel Moore, 2007; Varady 2002). Other factors, such as religion, religious orientation, age, and genetic predisposition, have just lately been investigated; nevertheless, a connection between the development of ED 3 and any of these factors has not been established. It is crucial, when it comes to the therapy as well as the prevention of EDs, to discover the relationships between the many distinct components of ED symptomology that are present (adherence to a religious tradition).

Keywords: *Religion Beliefs, Religion, Beliefs, Eating, Eating Disorders*

1. Introduction

Previous research has shown that there is a correlation between a person's degree of religious connection and their mental health. (Bergen, Masters, & Richards, 1987; Fabricatore, Handal, **THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

Rubio, & Gilner, 2004; Kendler, Liu, Gardner, McCullough, Larson, & Prescott, 2003; Pargament, 2002; Ryan, Rigby, and King, 1993). There is a relationship between having a strong internal religious orientation and having great mental health. This relationship may be seen as a connection. The symptoms of eating disorders are one of the things that this study intends to investigate, and one of its goals is to identify whether there is a relationship between religious inclination and those manifestations. Finding out whether there is a connection between eating disorders and the religious beliefs of a person is likely to be knowledge that will be relevant for the treatment of eating disorders in the future. Over the course of the last forty years, there has been a steady rise in the amount of interest shown by researchers in the part that spirituality and religion play in terms of mental health (Allport & Ross, 1967; Hardman, Barrett & Richards, 2003; Pargament, 2002). There are four distinct varieties of religious orientation, as hypothesized by Allport and Ross (1967), who established their idea in the same year. These are examples of intrinsic religiosity, which is also known as non-traditional religiosity, extrinsic religiosity, indiscriminate religiosity, and atheism. Other names for intrinsic religiosity include these other terms. People who have an inherent religious orientation make their religious practices a daily part of their life and look to the meaning and purpose they get from their beliefs as the source of purpose and importance in their lives. People who have an extrinsic religious orientation rely on their religion more than they do on themselves to live, and they may attend religious events for reasons related to their social lives or their families.

2. Non-Traditionally Religious Respond

People who are indiscriminately pro-religious or non-traditionally religious respond positively to any question perceived as religious on the Religious Orientation Scale (ROS), whereas people who indiscriminately non-religious or non-traditionally religious respond are negatively to questions perceived as religious on the ROS. This is because people who are indiscriminately pro-religious respond positively to any question perceived as religious on the ROS. Practice your faith. There has not been a lot of study conducted on this topic, and the conclusions are extremely conflicting and all over the place.

Previous research has shown that an intrinsic religious orientation is associated with better mental health, whereas the findings of other studies have shown that an extrinsic religious orientation is often associated with mental health problems (Bergin, Masters & Richards, 1987; Fabricatore, Handal, Rubio, & Gilner, 2004; Kendler, Liu, Gardner, McCullough, Larson & Prescott, 2003; Pargament, 2002; Ryan, Rigby & King, 1993). People who are not religious tend to have better mental health than people who are religious regardless of how much religiosity they espouse, but people who are religious without distinction are likely to have poorer mental health.

The findings of prior studies, in combination with the dearth of research that has been conducted on religion and eating disorders, have brought to light the importance of comprehending the connection that exists between religious temperament and EDs. Both those who are currently battling eating disorders and therapists will find this subject useful for the purposes of treatment as well as prevention of the problem. Although there have been studies conducted on the topic, the published research on the relationship between religion and eating problems is contradictory. Others emphasized the importance of spirituality or personal interactions with the sacred or divine in the process of helping those who are suffering from eating disorders, but no emphasis was placed on religious orientation or the reasons why people participate in religious practice. Some of the research on religion has focused on specific religious affiliations, such as Baptist, Methodist, or Jewish traditions (Dancyger et al., Others emphasized the importance of spirituality or personal interactions with the sacred or divine in the process of helping those who are suffering from eating disorders (Jacobs-Pilipski, Winzelberg, Wilfley, Bryson, & Taylor, 2005; Marsden, Karagianni and Morgan, 2007). Research that was conducted by Smith, Richards, and Maglio (2003) discovered a positive correlation between ED symptoms and extrinsic religiosity in the college women who attended Truman State Institution (TSU), which is a small university that can be found in the middle of the United States. among female patients at the Change Center who are undergoing residential treatment for eating problems.

3. Externally Religious or Indiscriminately Religious

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These researchers also found that those who were externally religious or indiscriminately religious tended to have more symptoms of eating disorders, while women who were devout or who practiced non-traditional forms of religion had less signs of eating disorders. In yet another research, Jewish women were questioned to discover the relationship between factors such as religious affiliation, mental health, the formation of negative body images, and eating disorders (Weinberger-Litman, 2008). The sample included 301 young adult women who attended either a high school or one of the two colleges located in New York City. The findings of this research indicated that women whose religious orientations were more intrinsically oriented had lower levels of body dissatisfaction, eating disorders, and fine ideal internalization than women whose religious orientations were extrinsic or indiscriminately pro-religious. Women who committed to faiths other than those traditionally followed did not show any statistically significant differences from other women. Additionally, Weinberger-Litman found that women who focused inwardly had less subtle ideal internalization than women who focused outwardly.

Considering these results, he hypothesized that the possession of an innate orientation may serve as a barrier against the development of EDs. Latter-day Saint (LDS) women had the greatest religious commitment (intrinsic) scores and the lowest EAT-26 scores, the results of a different research that examined the association between religious orientation and eating disorder symptoms found. On the other hand, highly intrinsic individuals who practiced faiths other than Christianity did not have lower scores on the EAT-26. Recent study conducted on women with LDS views who were enrolled in college hints at the possibility that age may function as a mediator in the connection that exists between religious orientation and the manifestation of eating disorder symptoms. Based on his experience at Brigham Young University, Winters (2005) utilized descriptive statistics to make an estimate of the number of LDS women who suffer from eating disorders. His research was published in 2005. He calculated that 9–11 percent of BYU women had a greater risk of eating disorders, with risk levels and eating disorder symptomology decreasing with each advancing year of college. He found that BYU women had a higher risk of eating disorders than women in the general population. In addition, Winters (2005) from Brigham Young University believes that the percentage of LDS women who struggle with eating disorders is between 9 and 11 percent.

Symptoms Tends to Lessen with Advancing Age

In addition, the results of a long-term research that was conducted by Heatherton, Mohammadi, Striepe, Field, and Keel (1997) show that the severity of ED symptoms tends to lessen with advancing age. After looking at 715 male and female college graduates, these researchers concluded that women's ED 6 symptoms, including bulimic vision, the desire to be slim, and overall symptoms, improved in the years after their graduation from college. The results of this study suggest that age may play a role as a mediator between the symptoms of ED and the risk factors that are involved. In a different investigation, Lock, Le Grange, Forsberg, and Hewell (2006) evaluated the efficacy of treatment by observing pre-teenagers and adolescents who suffered from eating disorders. The Eating Disorder Examination, or EDE, was given to a total of 110 individuals, and their scores as well as their symptoms were compared with those of the other group. According to the findings of the research that was conducted by Lock et al. (2006), it was found that the pre-treatment and post-treatment assessment ratings of adolescents were lower than those of adolescents. In addition to this, they found that prepubescent adolescents exhibit psychological and behavioral features that are equivalent to those of their contemporaries who are adolescents.

According to the results of this study, age may be an indication of how established ED symptoms are for distinct age groups, and the data suggest that younger persons may have less ED symptomology than senior folks have. These findings highlight the need for additional research aimed at better describing the link between eating disorder symptomology and religious orientation, as well as the question of whether this link is reduced by other factors such as age. Additionally, these findings highlight the question of whether this link is reduced by other factors such as age. Since the findings in this field do not always agree with one another, additional research might be helpful in determining whether there is a connection between eating disorders and religious orientation, as well as whether age is associated with or with the symptoms of eating disorders.

The Issue at Hand According to what was previously said, the findings of the many research studies that were conducted to investigate the connection between eating disorders and religious orientation in women of college age are inconclusive. In addition, there have only been a few of research that have studied the correlation between age and the manifestations of eating

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disorders. There is a need for more study on these connections utilizing standardized exams that consider big samples and age. The objective of this research was to examine a wider group of college-aged women to ascertain, via the application of established criteria, if there is a correlation between a person's religious orientation and the manifestations of eating disorders. In particular, the purpose of this research is to determine whether there is a connection between religiosity and the symptoms that are associated with eating disorders, considering the ages of the people who are participating in the analysis. 1. Is there a significant correlation between age, the existence of internal and external variables, and the interplay between these elements when evaluating eating disorder symptoms using the total EAT score? 2. Which of these characteristics, if any, serve as predictors of bulimia, diet, and oral control when evaluated against the subscales of the EAT when all of them are considered together? These three researchers collaborated on the study over its whole. The purpose of this research is to determine if there is a link between mentality and the signs of eating disorders in undergraduate students. Specifically, the participants will be asked about their eating habits and mentality.

4. Successful In Attracting Students

Participants Students in the Department of Religion at Brigham Young University (BYU), a large private university in the Western United States, were informed about the research and given the opportunity to participate in the research through an announcement that was made in the classes they were enrolled in. Students were also given the opportunity to gain experience more about the research online. The concerned university was able to recruit students from a broader variety of academic fields and grade levels inside the institution by holding these seminars. Additionally, the university was successful in attracting students who participated in these seminars. The researchers asked for volunteers to take part in the study by sending an advertisement to students enrolled in religion programs who were researching the subject. After providing a condensed description of the objectives of the study, they handed out forms to students and requested their participation in the research. After that, the students returned to the McKay School of Education at the time they had enrolled to participate in the survey and completed the questionnaire in one of the research rooms that were specifically dedicated for that purpose. The students were first provided with a piece of paper that asked for their informed

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permission. This paper included a comprehensive explanation of the objectives of the study as well as the participant's rights, including the ability to withdraw from participation in the research at any time. Subscales that were included in this test were Diet, Bulimia/Food Mind, and Oral Control. You have the choice of responding with " frequently," "usually," "often," "sometimes," "rarely," or "never" to this question. The EAT has shown a high degree of reliability and consistency, and it is acknowledged as a helpful screening tool in clinical and non-clinical contexts. [Case in point:] (Garner, Olmsted, Bohr, & Garfinkel, 1982; Garner & Garfinkel, 1979). The Religious Orientation Scale is a twenty-item instrument that investigates the aspects of an individual's internal as well as their exterior religious orientation (Allport & Ross, 1967). There are nine components that go into making up the internal subscale, and there are eleven elements that go into making up the exterior subscale. The Religious Orientation Scale, sometimes known as the ROS, is the most common religious orientation measurement used in the field of psychology of religion studies (Donahue, 1985).

Data An Excel file including the results of the demographic survey, EAT, and ROS was created by an advanced undergraduate student who was not otherwise involved in the project. This student did not take part in the research in any other manner than what was described above. This finding is in line with the findings of the study conducted by Smith et al. (2003), which discovered a positive relationship between extrinsic religious orientation and the symptomology of eating disorders. Women who were classified as having an extrinsic religious orientation or an indiscriminately religious attitude exhibited a greater incidence of eating disorder symptoms in both groups. This was true whether the women were identified as being more religious or less religious. Joughin et al. (1992) found that in a sample of more than 800 ED patients, higher levels of bulimia symptoms were associated with a weakening in the participants' religious beliefs in their self-perceived importance. These findings are consistent with Joughin et al(1992) .'s finding. Joughin et al. found that in a sample of more than 800 ED patients, higher levels of bulimia symptoms were associated with Joughin, and colleagues discovered that there was an association between these two factors in a sample of more than 800 ED patients. In addition, the purpose of this study was to determine whether an inherent religious orientation is linked to the symptomatology of eating disorders. There was no evidence to support the hypothesis that intrinsic motivation was a major factor in predicting a decrease in the severity of ED symptoms. On the other side, it has not been shown that an inherent

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relationship with religious or spiritual practice is positively connected with ED symptomology. This suggests that those who are religious or devoted in nature do not demonstrate a larger number of ED symptoms than those who are not religious or devout. This outcome is also consistent with the results of the research that was conducted by Smith and his colleagues (2003). The second phase of this investigation consisted of the researchers determining whether age was a major predictor of ED symptoms. In the multiple regression analysis, age was not shown to be a significant predictor of ED symptomology, nor was it proven to be a significant mediator of the relationship between religious orientation and ED symptoms. Both findings are consistent with the hypothesis that age does not play a significant role in the formation of either of these relationships. The findings of this study are subject to several restrictions. To start, the age range of participants was limited to be between 17 and 41 years old.

Research with participants spanning a broader variety of ages is likely to provide different findings. Second, there was only one religious affiliation that was well-represented, and the results may be more generalized to a population connected with a larger range of faiths if there had been greater religious diversity among the participants. This imbalance may be impacting the results and having more equal representation from each of the four groups might give significant information on the link between religious orientation and symptoms of eating disorders. Since the participants were not chosen at random, we are unable to generalize the results of this research to all female college students or even just to all the female college students who attend Brigham Young University. Despite the possibility that this study has a few shortcomings, it does possess several merits all the same. To begin, the study was successful since it included enough participants, which contributed to its overall power. Validated measures of religious orientation and the symptomology of eating disorders were used in this study, which helped to improve the reliability and validity of the findings. Third, a technique of statistics that considers several variables was used. This approach demonstrates the relationships between age, religious orientation, and the symptoms of eating disorders. It also identifies which variable has the highest correlation with eating disorder symptoms when the other two factors are present. Fourth, the participants in this research did not have a clear concept of the objectives of the investigation since it was a part of a bigger study that involved the use of a variety of different measuring instruments. Conclusion Since the nature of this study is relational, its findings cannot demonstrate a causal link between religious orientation

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and bulimic symptoms since they are correlational in nature. The results, on the other hand, suggest that a person's religious orientation could influence the bulimic symptoms they experience. Those women who participate in religious activities only for social or other non-internal motivations are likely to be at an increased risk of developing bulimia. Women who are more worried about how other people see them and how they look in public may be more susceptible to signals sent in their religious culture about the ideal body shape and appearance for women if they are also more concerned about how others view them.

5. Findings Of Our Investigation

The findings of our investigation do not give any evidence to support the idea that greater levels of intrinsic religious orientation relate to an increased risk of developing eating disorders. Researchers are going to concentrate their efforts in the future on conducting qualitative studies on college women who exhibit clinical or subclinical bulimic symptoms. The purpose of these studies will be to determine what signals these women are receiving concerning relevant religious beliefs, cultural norms, and body shape. A longitudinal study of women's religious orientation and eating disorder symptoms over time may also yield interesting results in this area and further assist in investigating the associations between eating disorders, age, and religious orientation. [Citation Relationships Between Different Religious Orientations and Eating Disorders The results of the present study may have implications for the therapeutic approaches used with people who are afflicted with eating disorders. This study contributes to the current body of research by expanding the body of empirical data suggesting that an extrinsic religiosity may be associated to bulimia symptoms. It is possible that patients may learn throughout the course of their therapy that discussing this issue is beneficial to their recovery from their eating problem. It is possible that therapists may wish to discuss how their patients perceive their own religious ideas, and patients should be open to examine how such beliefs may impact how they think about and behave in relation to eating disorders. Anorexia nervosa is defined by a failure to maintain a normal body weight, an excessive fear of gaining weight, a distorted sense of body size and form, and a loss of menstruation in postmenarcheal women. Anorexia nervosa is a mental disorder (the absence of three or more consecutive menstrual cycles). This great dread of gaining weight is not addressed by weight reduction; rather, it is

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amplified. Additionally, as the individual loses weight, their attempts to reduce weight grow more intense. The restrictive type of anorexia and the binge-eating/purging type of anorexia are the two subtypes of this eating disorder. Binge eating is not permitted as part of the restriction program, which also includes fasting, dieting, and strenuous exercise. The behaviors of binge eating, and purging include making oneself throw up after ingesting enormous quantities of food at one sitting and then purging the body of the food by using laxatives, diuretics, or enemas.

In addition to these physical manifestations, people who suffer from anorexia rely their sense of self-worth and their values on their body weight and form (Daniels, 2009). Binge eating, vomiting, and having a low self-esteem that is influenced by one's body shape and weight are the defining characteristics of the mental illness known as bulimia nervosa (DSM-IV-TR, 2000). An individual is said to be binge eating when they consume more food in a certain period (typically less than two hours) than the average person can consume in the same length of time. In addition, the individual has the impression that they have no control over their episodes of binge eating and often continues to eat until they are so full that it is uncomfortable. People who suffer from bulimia nervosa do not engage in binge eating in a single sitting, and it is important to consider the surroundings of their intake (for example, a celebratory or holiday meal is not typically considered a binge). The removal of the substance may be performed using self-induced vomiting, laxatives, diuretics, or enemas, as well as through the abuse of these substances. Eating disorders have also been linked to a variety of personality disorders (PD), such as borderline personality disorder, avoidant personality disorder, obsessive-compulsive personality disorder, and paranoid personality disorder (Ro, Martinsen, Hoffart, & Rosenvinge, 2005; Spindler & Milos, 2004). It is anticipated that the treatment of mental problems will cost an additional \$147 billion more than treating cancer, respiratory disease, or AIDS, but the expenses are simply enormous and difficult to quantify (WHO, 2004). Treatment for eating disorders may be very expensive, both from a medical and a psychological perspective. Treatment for eating disorders is projected to cost around 6 billion dollars annually according to estimates (Duncan, 2005; NEDA, 2008). The costs of treatment include visits to a primary care physician, hospitalization for treatment, lost time at work or school, and the cost of compensating for occupational or educational impairment. Both the long-term nature of eating disorders and the high occurrence of comorbid conditions are factors that contribute to the

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increased expense of therapy (Simon, Schmidt, & Pilling, 2005). Usually, people with eating disorders are treated by their primary care physician for psychiatric or gastrointestinal issues, and the fundamental concern of the eating disorder is not addressed (Simon et al., 2005).

Anorexia nervosa has the highest mortality rate of any psychiatric disorder, partly due to higher suicide rates (Birmingham, Su, Hlynsky, Goldner, and Gao). This is in addition to the medical problems, social or interpersonal problems, and the prohibitive cost of treatment that are associated with the condition. Even though bulimia nervosa and EDNOS do not have as high a mortality rate as anorexia nervosa does, it is still possible to pass away because of these eating disorders (Crow, Praus, & Thuras 1999). Stice (2001) discovered that among the prevalent mental illnesses, eating disorders had the greatest rates of seeking treatment, hospitalization, and attempted suicide out of all the disorders studied. Eating disorders also serve as a predictor for the development of obesity, which in turn leads to an increased risk of morbidity and mortality (Stice, 2001). The prohibitive cost of treatment for eating disorders and the high mortality rates associated with them make eating disorders a problem for the public's health.

Causes and Origins of Eating Disorders The study of eating disorders has shown that these conditions may be brought on by a wide variety of circumstances, and that there is no one component that is solely responsible for the development of eating disorders. The link between eating disorders is not completely understood, which contributes to the fact that risk variables interact together to raise the risk of eating disorders. WHO (2004) identified certain concerns about body image as risk factors? These include excessive dieting, excessive concerns about shape or weight, and dissatisfaction with one's body. An elevated level of body fat, being unhappy with one's appearance and one's weight, following a diet that restricts calories and going through stressful life transitions are all other physical risk factors (Carroll & Spangler, 2002; Stice, 2001). Dissatisfaction with one's appearance as well as one's diet can both be indicators of the onset of major depression (Stice, 2001). It was discovered by Franko and Striegel-Moore (2007) that gender, ethnicity, concerns about shape and weight, childhood eating, and gastrointestinal problems may all play a role in the development of eating disorders. Overeating is a predictor of bulimic pathology and having a negative affect or a tendency to experience emotional distress may both encourage overeating (Stice, 2001).

6. Factors That Are Social and Emotional

In Nature Low levels of media literacy, internalization of the thin ideal of the media, family beliefs about weight and shape, and sociocultural pressures to be thin are all examples of family and social influences that contribute to obesity (Carroll & Spangler, 2002; Stice, 2001; WHO, 2004). Wiseman, Gray, Moismann, and Ahrens (1992) discovered that the culturally desirable body shape became increasingly slender over time. Furthermore, between the years 1979 and 1988, contestants for the Miss America pageant weighed an average of 15 percent less than what was expected for their age and height. The cultural ideal of having a smaller body contributes to an increase in dissatisfaction with one's own physique, as well as unhealthy eating behaviors and eating disorders (Carroll & Spangler, 2002). Grenfell (2006) also discussed the impact that individuals' religious beliefs have on their perceptions of their bodies, particularly the emphasis placed on religion's control over the individual's body in terms of spiritual and bodily cleanliness, dress codes, and sexual purity. Grenfell (2006) also discussed the impact that individuals' religious beliefs have on their perceptions of their bodies. This results in a feeling that the role of an individual's body is becoming more important and imposes cultural ideals on what a person does with their body. Other Potential Danger Factors Low self-esteem is one of the most common risk factors for perfectionism, along with physical and sexual abuse, insecure attachment, difficulty in dealing with stress, poor self-evaluation, and over-focusing on perfection (Franko & Striegel-Moore, 2007; Stice, 2001; WHO, 2004). There is some evidence that elevated levels of perfectionism and self-esteem, when combined with other risk factors, might increase the likelihood of developing an eating problem. Multivariate models concentrating on the interaction between many risk variables have been presented. For example, Bruch (1973) was the first to define persons who suffer from eating disorders as feeling out of control. She claimed that females who acquire eating problems do this to obtain control over their bodies. Since then, the role of control in eating disorders and the question of where the locus of control lies have been the primary focuses of researchers (Berg, 2001; Varady, 2002).

People who have eating disorders may have the perception that they lack control over many facets of their life; as a result, they may attempt to make up for this perceived lack of control by using their eating disorder as a means to attain a feeling of control over their lives (Hardman, Berrett, & Richards, 2003; Rezek & Leary, 1991). The researchers Rezek and Leary (1991)

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discovered that a loss of control, particularly in interpersonal situations, might provoke reactions that a loss of control in impersonal environments does not, and that this can condition an individual to engage in control exercise via an eating problem. In addition, Rezek and Leary discovered that perceived liking (the extent to which the subjects believed that the listener liked them), social rejection, and social anxiety all had an impact on perceived control. According to Richards, Smith, Berrett, O'Grady, and Bartz (2009), individuals who struggle with eating disorders may have ten dysfunctional beliefs, some of which include the following: "Both "my eating disorder will validate me from others" and "my eating disorder will give me control over my life and emotions" can be rephrased as "my eating disorder will give me control over these things" (p. 174). These beliefs tend to drive those who struggle with eating disorders farther away from their families, friends, and even higher powers or gods. The percentage (n) of the study's parents who responded to questions concerning their religious practices during pregnancy, broken down by a variety of demographic factors. Age and Eating Disorders: According to Pyle, Neuman, Halvorson, and Mitchell (1984) and the World Health Organization (2004), the average age of onset for anorexia nervosa is between 14 and 18, and the average age of onset for bulimia nervosa occurs during the transitional period between adolescence and adulthood. These findings pertain to university-aged women who exhibit symptoms of an eating disorder.

7. Possibility Of Experiencing Pain

The possibility of experiencing pain is extremely high. It is more likely for a person to develop an eating disorder if they are away from their family and friends, if they are exposed to higher levels of stress, if they feel pressured to succeed academically, and if they have less social support (Winters, 2005). College-aged women may be at a greater risk of developing eating problems due to social contagion as well as increased rivalry among married spouses (Winters, 2005). Eating Disorder Examination (EDE) was applied to 110 people aged 9-18.5 years, and the results of the examination, including symptomology and score comparisons, were analyzed. While the mean age before puberty was 11.9 years, the mean age of teenagers was 15.5 years. According to the results of Lock et al., pre-, and post-adolescent evaluation scores were lower than teenagers. In addition to this, they found that prepubescent adolescents exhibit

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psychological and behavioral features that are equivalent to those of their contemporaries who are adolescents. According to the results of this study, age may reliably predict the severity of ED symptoms across age groups and may also impact both the effectiveness of therapy and the risk factors connected with EDs. Research over the past 40 years has focused on the role of religiosity in mental health, focusing especially on the association between the two (Allport & Ross, 1967; Bergin, Masters & Richards, 1987; Fallot, 2007; Pargament, 2002). . According to the conclusions of this research, it is not enough to ask someone if they are "spiritual" or "religious"; rather, it is required to analyze the causes that encourage a person to participate in spiritual activities. Definition of Spirituality and Religion Researchers typically create a difference between religious practice and spirituality in the operational definitions they employ in their study. For instance, Fallot (2007) defines spirituality as the component of a person's inner experience that is divine, ultimate, or transcendent. On the other hand, religious practice has a component of organization and often necessitates the involvement of a community of believers who are committed to the same religious rites and beliefs. Richards and Bergin (2005) define spirituality as the pursuit and harmony of "God or Divine Intelligence that governs or harmonizes the universe," while Pargament (2002) defines religiosity as "the search for meaning in relevant ways." Richards and Bergin (2005) define spirituality as the pursuit and harmony of "God or Divine Intelligence that governs or harmonizes the universe." " (Spirituality and religiosity are not synonymous).

According to Oomen (2000), an individual's dedication to a Higher Power via the practice of organized religion or a belief system is an illustration of their religiosity. (p. 4). When studying the perspectives of persons with eating disorders It may be crucial to differentiate between religiosity and spirituality in this context since these persons may have narrow viewpoints on religion but may utilize spirituality in accordance with its expanded meaning and in several different contexts. After conducting a literature review, Fallot (2007) concluded, based on his findings, that religiosity has the potential to either serve as a buffer and support system for people who struggle with mental health problems or to exacerbate the impact that their mental health problems have on them. Allport and Ross (1967), Pargament (2002), Fabricatore, Handal, Rubi Research by he and Gilner (2004) and Kendler, Liu, Gardner, McCullough, Larson, and Prescott give evidence in support of this concept. (These academics investigated

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many facets of religion, such as personal dedication, inner motivation, compassion, general piety, religious coping, and forgiveness.

It is crucial to know research on the link between religion and well-being has yielded contradicting conclusions. This is due, in part, to the many ways in which well-being has been defined. On the other hand, when well-being is defined in terms of religious orientation as opposed to psychosocial orientation, there is a link between well-being and better mental health. This is because religiously oriented people tend to have more positive attitudes about life in general (Pargament, 2002). The Connection Between Extramural Religion and Psychological Well-Being The difference between extrinsic and intrinsic religious characteristics, as well as the effects of both types of variables on an individual's mental health, has been the primary focus of study on religious views. According to Allport and Ross (1967), those who utilize their religion rather than living it are considered to have an extrinsic attitude to religion. This definition may be found in the authors' work. People who have this syndrome could address church to distract themselves from their troubles, socialize, elevate their status, or feel more comfortable in their lives. According to Pargament (2002), extrinsic religiosity is described as a forced, unexamined, and reflection of an unstable relationship with God. Extrinsic religiosity reflects an unstable connection with God. Additionally, he concluded that an extrinsic religious orientation was deleterious to one's mental health. Allport and Ross (1967) concluded that the effects of external religious practices on mental health were negative, but the effects of internal religious factors on mental health were positive. Individuals who have lower levels of intrinsic religiosity also have greater levels of internal tension and conflict, as well as an external locus of control, according to the findings of study conducted by Ryan, Rigby, and King (1993). When persons with an extrinsic religious orientation participate in religious rituals, they typically do so out of a feeling of obligation or guilt, or because they think they would feel uncomfortable if they do not engage in these behaviors. On the other hand, Allport and Ross (1967) defined people as having an innate religious orientation if they are guided by religion, living their religion rather than using it, and if so. These three conditions must be met for a person to be considered to have an innate religious orientation.

There is a correlation between engaging in activities that are intrinsic to one's religion and improvements in one's mental health as well as an overall increase in enjoyment of life.

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Pargament (2002), for instance, established that there are consistent connections between healthy types of religious coping and better mental health outcomes. Falloot (2007) observed in his review that older persons with depressive symptoms who are inherently religious had a shorter time to feel remission from their symptoms than adults who were outwardly religious or agnostic. To promote mental health, one's religious activities must be internalized, driven by their own inner aspirations, and founded on a secure relationship with God (Pargament, 2002). (Pargament, 2002). Higher levels of intrinsic religiosity have been associated with decreased levels of anxiety, depression, and social dysfunction (Ryan), in addition to increased sociability, a sense of well-being, and intellectual productivity (Bergin, Masters, & Richards, 1987). (People who have a higher level of intrinsic religiosity and participate in spiritual activities have the capacity to cope better with stressful situations and experience less stress overall) (Jacobs-Pilipski, Winzelberg, Wilfley, Bryson, & Taylor, 2005). Individuals can build a greater ability to let go of control and let God rule their life when they participate in activities that are fundamentally religious. This satisfies the fundamental urge that people must feel in charge of their lives (Krause, 2009). Often, these individuals have the mentality that God will help them to be more in control of their lives, as opposed to the perception that God controls their lives. An Example of Harmful Impact Caused by Religion According to Pargament (2002), religious activities may be detrimental or useful depending on the kind of religion, well-being criteria, individual, circumstance, and social environment. Additionally, these consequences are altered by the degree to which a person is personally committed in their faith. Religious notions can have a damaging influence on an individual's self-image and self-concept.

It is possible to define perfectionism as a personal ideal, attitude, or ideology that rejects everything that is imperfect and instead demands that perfection be achieved. Desire for approval from others, self-hatred, unfavorable ideas about God, overconfidence, fatigue, and bipolar thinking are some of the adverse repercussions that may emerge from perfectionism (Edgington et al., 2008). (Edgington et al., 2008). According to the findings of Richards et al. (2009), when people are unable to fulfill their religious obligations, they exhibit less religious behavior and have a greater sense of alienation from God. This is because they feel they have failed to live up to their religious responsibilities. This conclusion was also seen in the research that Hardman, Berrett, and Richards (2003) conducted in which they looked at the dysfunctional beliefs that were held by women who were battling eating disorders. A good many of these

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beliefs divert individuals who are battling with eating disorders from their believe in God and encourage them to invest their hopes and relies in their eating disorder rather than in God. Practicing a Religion May Bring About Beneficial Results On the other side, people's lives may improve under the influence of their religious beliefs. Edgington et al. (2008) found several beneficial aspects that may result from holding religious beliefs. These themes include personal openness, acceptance of both oneself and one's faults, belief in a loving God, and surrendering to or accepting of God's grace in one's life. All these ideas can originate from a person's adherence to a particular religious tradition. When individuals were at last able to disentangle their religious beliefs from the judgements, they had previously made about themselves, this is when they arrived at these concepts. According to the results of Richards, Hardman, and Berrett (2007), persons who have religious views have a connection to a higher power, and as a result, they can feel and display greater love and compassion. These researchers also discovered that people who believe in a higher power have a greater capacity for love and compassion toward one another. The Function and Importance of Spirituality in the Recuperation Process Despite the fact that most people consider themselves to be spiritual (Frazier, 2007; Pew Forum, 2010), research into the relationship between spirituality and treatment has received very little attention. Two explanations for this phenomenon are the fact that academics and theorists disagree about the role that spirituality plays in therapy and the fact that a much smaller percentage of therapists are personally engaged in religious or spiritual activities.

Both factors contribute to the phenomenon (Frazier, 2007; Hathaway, Scott, & Garver, 2004). While Freud believed that spirituality is an illusion that prevents people from confronting reality, Jung indicated that it requires a transcendent experience to provide individuals with the necessary energy to resist the temptations of the outer world. Freud's argument may be found here (Westgate, 1996). To describe the harmony that exists between himself and a higher power, Maslow utilized the idea of a transcendent self-actualizer. There are some therapists and researchers working in the field of mental health care today who have similar intense emotional reactions and points of view about the part that spirituality may play in the therapeutic process. Others might not be aware of the potential part that spirituality can play in treatment until treatment surveys of patients show that 34% of patients indicate that spirituality was a beneficial component in their recovery (Hsu, Crisp, & Callender, 1992; Mitchell, Erlander, Pyle, & Fletcher, 1989).

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8. Results

Beginning in the 1960s, mental health professionals gradually began to acknowledge the significance of the part that spirituality plays in the treatment process (Blanch, 2007). Abraham Maslow, Victor Frankl, and others developed this branch of study because they were interested in the connection that exists between spirituality and mental health (Blanch, 2007). Research on eating disorders and spirituality is limited (for instances, see Berrett, Hardman, O'Grady, & Richards, 2008; Dell & Josephson, 2007). The number of research studies on spirituality and mental health is increasing (for example, research on the spiritual underpinnings of addiction and improving mental health), but there has been little investigation into the relationship between spirituality and eating disorders.

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